

1 **Mex3a and Mex3b function in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Mex3a
8 and Mex3b as lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 Citations

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